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INDIVIDUAL PROJECT

Dimples Optimisation on NACA 4412 and Their Applications

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Abstract:

This study investigates the aerodynamic shape optimisation of the NACA 4412 aerofoil through surface modifications using dimples, aiming to delay flow separation, reduce pressure drag, and improve the L/D ratio. A systematic CFD approach in ANSYS Fluent was applied to both 2D and 3D models. The 2D study first tested single and then dual-dimple, identifying rectangular dimples at 0.55c and 0.75c chord positions as optimal, reducing drag by up to 14% compared to the clean aerofoil at a stalling angle (14°), but triangular dimples occasionally increased drag. At 6° AoA, rectangular dual-dimple at 0.35c and 0.75c compared to the single dimple at 0.75c shows a 6.9% increase in L/D ratio. The study highlights that dual-dimple spaced farther apart outperformed the ones closer to each other, particularly at AoA, which is relevant to take-off and landing (0° – 20°).

The results of 2D dual-dimple study were extended to 3D by extruding the aerofoil to 3D wing; dimple density was varied along the span of an Aeronca 11AC Chief aircraft wing, with dual-dimple designs (extruded and equally spaced) showing better efficiency compared to clean wing simulation. While 2D results showed delayed stall and flow separation, the 3D study encountered difficulties due to computational constraints, emphasising the importance of refined mesh strategies and experimental validation. The study further develops a framework for optimising dimples on the NACA 4412 aerofoil with potential applications in sports and training aircraft. However, dimpled wings must undergo structural integrity assessments via FEA before real-world implementation.

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Abbreviations:

CFD – Computational Fluid Dynamics
FEA – Finite Element Analysis
AR – Aspect Ratio
c – chord length
AoA – Angle of Attack
C_L – Lift Coefficient
C_D – Drag Coefficient
C_p – Pressure Coefficient
LE – Leading Edge
TE – Trailing Edge
L/D – Lift to Drag Ratio
Re – Reynolds Number
RANS – Reynolds-averaged Navier-Stokes
 ϵ – turbulence dissipation rate
 ω – specific turbulence dissipation rate

1. Introduction

The primary objective to optimise the aircraft wing is to enhance airborne performance, including manoeuvrability and aerodynamic efficiency. One approach to achieving this is through passive surface modifications on aircraft wings. By analysing where the flow separates over the aerofoil surface as the AoA is increased these modifications help delaying flow separation and promote turbulent boundary layer transition. This leads to improved flow attachment to the surface hence improve aerodynamic efficiency, giving higher L/D ratio, ultimately delaying stall and allowing aircraft to operate at higher AoAs. Such improvements can be beneficial in aviation, from military aircraft requiring manoeuvrability to commercial planes needing fuel efficiency and passenger safety.

With optimal dimple size, location and shape can greatly improve the performance of aircraft. The ability of the aircraft to generate less drag and more lift during flight means that it has better aerodynamic efficiency, thereby improving fuel consumption. Given current environmental and global warming threats to aviation industry, the emphasis is on reducing the CO₂ emissions. Drag-reduction techniques help reducing the CO₂ emission by decreasing the power and fuel required for flight operation hence reducing operation cost. The similar dimple addition technique can be applied to wind turbine blades where dimples manage BL turbulence and delay flow separation and reducing drag thereby ultimately enhancing L/D ratio.

The research examines the impact of dimples when placed on the upper surface of an aerofoil moving from the LE to TE, analysing near stall AoAs, with the expectations to delay stall. Testing different dimple shapes, sizes and chordwise location, the researcher seek to access the impacts of such suction surface modification on the aerofoil performance. The objective is to determine the optimal dimple design which improves aircrafts performance under subsonic conditions. The research utilises computational CFD model for 2D analysis to understand the flow behaviour around the altered NACA4412 aerofoil, with extension to 3D simulations.

1.1 Background Study on Dimples

The golf ball is the primary example of a bluff body with dimples, a tiny surface indentation that influences airflow behaviour compared to the smooth spherical ball. A critical question arises: How does a dimpled surface yield better aerodynamic performance than a smooth surface? Dimples function by controlling boundary layer separation, a phenomenon where the airflow detaches from the surface, creating a large wake that increases drag and reduces lift.

Figure 1 highlights the aerodynamic disparity between a dimpled golf ball and a smooth sphere. On the golf ball, the dimples promote airflow attachment by inducing a turbulent boundary layer across the upper surface. This turbulence delays flow separation, reducing the wake behind the ball. In contrast, the dimpled surface facilitates an early transition to a turbulent boundary layer, which increases skin friction drag but delays flow separation. The turbulent flow remains attached to the surface longer, minimising wake size and pressure drag. Although the dimpled design incurs higher pressure drag than a smooth surface, the net drag reduction from the smaller wake outweighs this penalty, leading to enhanced aerodynamic performance. Conversely, the smooth sphere exhibits laminar airflow with lower skin friction drag. However, this laminar flow separates prematurely, creating an extensive turbulent wake. The resulting pressure drag from this larger wake significantly impedes forward motion compared to the dimpled design.

Figure 1: Smooth sphere vs Golf ball flow behaviour and wake formation [1]

1.2 Aim and Objectives

This study aims to optimise dimples to improve aerodynamic performance.

Objectives:

- Conduct a rigorous mesh independence study to validate computational methodology using Ansys Fluent and validate the results.
- Investigate the aerodynamic impact of varying dimple shapes (semi-circular, trapezoidal, triangular) and sizes (diameter, depth) on the upper surface and compare performance metrics (lift, drag, stall)
- Test dimple locations along the chord to identify regions (e.g., near LE, mid-chord, TE) that maximise lift-to-drag ratios or delay flow separation.
- Determine the most effective dual-dimple geometry and location based on aerodynamic efficiency.
- Extend the optimal 2D dimple configuration to a 3D NACA 4412 wing model, incorporating spanwise dimple density and distribution.
- Analyse aerodynamic behaviour (pressure distribution, tip vortices) at multiple angles of attack (0° – 20°) under subsonic conditions.
- Discuss implications of findings on real-world applications, such as sports airplanes with the aim to improve aerodynamic efficiency and delaying stall.

2. Literature Review

The motive of this research is to improve the aerodynamic efficiency of aircraft wings, as it directly influences manoeuvrability, fuel efficiency, and overall performance, thereby reducing operational costs. The study explores surface modification through dimples to enhance aerodynamic performance. Dimples delay flow separation and reduce pressure drag by inducing turbulence in the boundary layer. Turbulence increases the energy of the boundary layer, allowing it to remain attached to the wing's suction surface longer, converting potential energy into kinetic energy and minimising wake formation.

The concept draws inspiration from the golf ball effect, where dimples improve aerodynamic properties by increasing the L/D ratio and delaying stall. For passenger aircraft, drag reduction is pivotal for lowering fuel consumption, while for acrobatic aircraft, dimples can enhance handling characteristics. Additionally, optimising dimple shapes may further streamline airflow, reducing wake turbulence and improving aerodynamic efficiency.

By creating a turbulent boundary layer that adheres to the wing surface more effectively than a laminar layer, dimples delay flow separation. This enhances lift and reduces drag,

particularly at higher angles of attack, contributing to improved performance during critical phases like take-off and landing.

2.1 Theory

It is essential to study boundary layer formation to understand the theory behind dimples and how they impact flow separation. When the flow travels at velocity U_∞ in the freestream direction, it interacts with the (body) upper (suction surface) and lower (pressure surface) of the aerofoil. The no-slip condition applies as the air encounters the body; it is a basic phenomenon:

1. The Air close to the surface is stationary: Due to the surface roughness and intermolecular forces, air molecules right next to the aerofoil tend to adhere to it. Thereby they do not slip over the surface relative to it.
2. The Boundary layer is formed: A thin layer of air, known as the boundary layer, is developed close to the surface. Within this layer, effects of air viscosity (the "stickiness" of air) are most manifested.
3. Velocity increases gradually: From zero at the surface, the speed of the air increases as one moves away from the aerofoil until it attains the free-stream speed, the speed of air well away from the surface.
4. Shear stress develops: Because of the variation in velocity within the boundary layer, friction and shear stress developed. This shear stress is critical regarding the magnitude of drag, or air resistance, and lift forces developed on the aerofoil.
5. Separation may occur: When the angle of attack is high, meaning that the aerofoil is highly inclined, the boundary layer may not stick to the surface, and the flow separates. It affects the production of lift of the aerofoil and gives more drag [2].

Figure 2: demonstrating boundary layer and thickness formation on an aerofoil [2]

A boundary layer forms as shown in Figure 2 on the upper surface, and the flow remains attached to the surface depending on factors such as the AoA, flow speed, and surface

roughness characteristics. Laminar flow occurs when the air moves in smooth, parallel layers with minimal disturbance. In contrast, turbulent flow is characterised by chaotic swirls, where the air moves in multiple directions, and the speed continuously varies in magnitude and direction. At a certain point, referred to as the separation point (see Figure 3), the flow detaches from the surface. This transition marks the laminar to turbulent flow, meaning the flow will form wakes and within this region no lift will be produced from the surface of the aerofoil.

Figure 3: illustrates the boundary layer and flow separation point over a surface [3]

As we increase the AoA, pressure on the upper surface of the aerofoil decreases while it increases on the lower surface. Moreover, an adverse pressure gradient is a condition where static pressure increases in the flow direction. Increasing adverse pressure gradient leads to flow separation when the gradient is too strong; however, with dimples on the aerofoil, the separation point moves forward, and stall delays. Moreover, the stall also depends on the Re, the higher the Re number, the earlier the stall. The aircraft stalling point will be determined by constantly increasing the AoA.

2.2 Background Research

The background research identifies several challenges and trade-offs, such as how dimples reduce pressure drag significantly and slightly increase friction drag due to the turbulence they create. Optimising these factors is essential to balance drag reduction with lift enhancement. A primary focus in this quest for efficiency is surface modification on aerofoils, particularly dimple designs that reduce drag and enhance manoeuvrability.

In the study by Singh and R. H. [5], dimples were positioned at 66% of the chord length from the LE. Following their recommendations, this research evaluates semi-circular semi-rectangular, triangle and trapezoidal dimples. A "smart dimple matrix" concept, proposed by [6], introduces an adaptive design for optimising dimple placement. A critical

consideration is the transition point, as dimples should ideally be placed where flow separation begins. This strategy aims to maintain attached flow for longer durations, promoting turbulent boundary layer development toward the TE and delaying separation. However, dimple effectiveness depends on aerofoil geometry, requiring a tailored designs for different aerofoils (profile).

Studies demonstrate that surface modifications like dimples enhance aircraft efficiency. For instance, dimples on the surface can reduce drag by up to 6.6% through airflow stabilisation and delayed separation [4]. Consequently, dimpled aerofoils may achieve higher L/D ratio compared to smooth surfaces. Prior research by Srivastav et al. [7,8] on NACA 0018 aerofoils revealed that dimples improve aerodynamic efficiency and manoeuvrability. Similarly, Livya et al. [9] demonstrated through CFD that dimpled configurations reduce drag, delay boundary layer separation, and enhance stall angles. However, turbulent transition near the TE raises skin friction drag, complicating drag coefficient trends: while separation delays may initially reduce drag, turbulence can increase overall drag despite lower skin friction in laminar regions.

Bhadri Rajasai et al. and Tai et al. [18] highlighted that dimple on NACA 2412 suction surface reduces skin friction drag and increases lift compared to the clean case configuration. For example, Singh and R. H. [5] emphasise that drag-reduction strategies for wings cannot be universally applied due to variations in camber, thickness, and flow dynamics among NACA profiles. Discrepancies in prior findings underscore the need for further investigation into dimple size, placement, and aerofoil-specific optimisation.

Existing literature lacks comprehensive analysis of dual-dimple configuration. However, these studies consistently shows that NACA aerofoils can achieve better aerodynamic performance thus improving L/D ratio by addition of dimples. Previous studies show that for wind turbine applications dimples on suction and pressure surface can improve their aerodynamic performance. However, for aviation applications dimples only on suction surface are required due to the flow behaviour. Flow on the suction surface detaches on aircraft wing whereas flow on the pressure surface stay laminar and undergoes smooth transition.

From the previous findings on dimple addition on symmetrical aerofoils highlight their capacity to enhance aerodynamic efficiency, suggesting that similar benefits could extend to cambered profiles such as the NACA4412 through systematic optimisation. The findings from the previous studies. reveals a critical interdependence between aerodynamic performance outcomes with dimple position, size and variation in AoA, underscoring the need for rigorous parametric analyses covering possible operational scenarios, including varied Reynolds numbers and turbulence intensities. Moreover, the previous studies also

utilise the ANSYS Fluent application making it more reliable for exploring these design variables.

This study computationally evaluates dimple placement (LE, mid-chord, TE) on the NACA 4412 aerofoil to optimise boundary layer adhesion, with a focus on shapes and sizes of dimples that reduce drag, increase lift, and delay stall at high angles of attack. Building on prior validation of clean aerofoil data against existing research [12], the work extends beyond conventional single-dimple analyses by testing dual-dimple. By prioritising inward dimples, assessed for their influence on flow separation and pressure distribution, the research targets practical aerospace applications, particularly for aircraft and gliders reliant on the NACA 4412 profile. Results aim to establish whether dual-dimple positioning can outperform traditional single-dimple in sustaining aerodynamic efficiency under demanding flight conditions.

3. Methodology

3.1 Software Utilised

In this computational investigation, three primary software packages were employed for modelling, simulation, and post-processing. The aerofoil geometry was initially designed in SolidWorks ensuing sharp trailing edge and curved blended leading edge. Later using SolidWorks, the suction surface of aerofoil was modified. The geometries were then imported into Ansys Workbench to construct the fluid domain, which was subsequently discretised using a meshing tool. A detailed description of these procedures is outlined in Section 3.2. Ansys Fluent, a pressure-based CFD solver, served as the primary tool for simulating incompressible flows by solving the Navier-Stokes equations which express momentum and energy balance. During the simulation Fluid Flow (Fluent) solver performs two critical tasks, first it converges the flow monitoring all governing equations (mass, momentum and energy conservation) residuals. The residuals must drop which indicates stability and accuracy of the solver. Second, after convergence solver provide tools for extracting the meaningful insights from simulating data and this includes generating contours, path-lines and from report definitions lift and drag forces. The results such as C_L and C_D at specific angle of attack were extracted and Python was used to generate visual plots. Furthermore, XFOIL, open source CFD software tool, was used for quick simulation and the results were compared with Ansys fluent 2D simulation. As the simulation on Ansys Fluent takes long to solve, MobaXterm was employed to execute Ansys Fluent case files remotely on the University of Southampton's Iridis 5 supercomputer to enhance computational efficiency. This approach significantly reduces simulation runtime compared to local processing via Ansys Fluent alone, while ensuring numerical accuracy.

3.2 Research Design

A systematic computational approach was developed to enhance aerodynamic performance of NACA 4412 by addition of dimples on the aerofoil. First, a 2D CFD framework was selected to analyse flow behaviour with clean and dimple configurations, balancing accuracy with computational efficiency via iterative dimple optimisation approach. The research employs quantitative methods based on numerical simulations, leveraging Reynolds-averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) equations to resolve viscous flow interactions and accurately capturing the physics of boundary layer. Various dimple shapes and locations were analysed, and dimples were placed on the suction surface at various locations including key regions such as leading edge, mid-chord, trailing edge. Later 3D study was conducted based on the results of 2D study. The focus on quantitative CFD, enables systematic evaluation on how dimple shapes at suction surface influence transitional flow dynamics and aerodynamic efficiency.

3.2.1 Two-Dimensional Aerofoil CFD

The 2D CFD setup and simulation process is discussed in this section.

3.2.1.1 Aerofoil Geometry

The NACA4412 aerofoil (depicted in Figure 4) which has an asymmetrical profile and has well rounded performance across various flight conditions effectively managing lift and drag as AoA changes. Given the aerofoil's predictable stall characteristics [10] and diverse applications in aviation industry (discussed in section 5). NACA 4412 was selected for further investigation into whether the addition of dimples could enhance its aerodynamic performance.

Figure 4: illustrates NACA 4412 aerofoil based on x y and z coordinates

Aerofoil coordinates were generated using a NACA aerofoil generator tool from 200 number of points [16]. A sharp, closed trailing edge was produced with the chord of 1 meter. To ensure high-fidelity aerofoil representation in the SolidWorks, the initial coordinates were first processed in XFOIL, where the number of defining points was increased from 200 to 400 to better capture curvature and maintain geometric precision. These 400 points, containing updated x, y, and z coordinates, were then imported into the SolidWorks

and converted the coordinates into smooth, continuous splines. This step minimises discretisation errors that could otherwise distort the computational mesh, around the curvature and sharp end particularly near leading and trailing edge.

3.2.1.2 Domain

The C-type domain (see Figure 5) is used due to its effective alignment with the aerofoil surface and wake region, making it well-suited for capturing viscous flow. Its structured grid generation allows high-quality orthogonal elements near the boundary layer and wake regions, improving numerical stability and solution accuracy resulting in flow convergence. C-grids optimise cell distribution, reducing unnecessary clustering in non-critical regions and lowering computational expense [13]. However, a limitation occurs with blunt trailing edges, where turbulence modelling accuracy may be compromised. The domain dimensions were set to $15c$ in the streamwise direction, with a diameter of $10c$ as suggested by Ali Elham [14]. This configuration allows the inlet flow to stabilise before reaching the aerofoil, which was positioned in region 2 at $5c$ from the inlet. Additionally, a $10c$ was maintained between the TE and the domain outlet to ensure proper wake capture. This setup balances computational efficiency with adequate flow development and further expanding the domain would unnecessarily increase mesh size and computation time without providing significant benefits. Given its advantages in resolving boundary layers, flow separation, and wake dynamics, the C-grid remains an optimal choice for high-fidelity aerofoil CFD analysis. Furthermore, Boolean operator applied, subtracting the aerofoil from the domain so that final aerofoil shape is created hence flow can pass over it.

Figure 5: depicts domain and aerofoil with highlighted regions

3.2.1.3 Meshing

Hybrid meshing (see Figure 6) approach was adopted to balance computational efficiency and accuracy in the aerofoil simulation. The domain was strategically split into two regions: Region 1 (outer domain) used a coarser element sizing of 0.1 m, while Region 2 (near the aerofoil) employed a finer sizing of 0.009 m for accurately capturing flow near the aerofoil. Edge sizing was controlled with 500 divisions along critical sections to maintain smooth transitions and minimise skewness. Near the inlet and leading edge, a structured mesh was applied to maintain high-quality nodes distribution which takes lower computational memory and better numerical stability and solver convergence. Moving towards the outlet and TE, an unstructured mesh was employed in region 2, the refined zone, to better adapt complex flow features like wake development and flow separation.

A mesh independence study (see Table 1 and 2) was conducted to determine the optimal grid resolution, finding a balance between computational cost and solution accuracy. To accurately resolve boundary layer effects, an inflation layer with 40 prism layers was applied near the aerofoil surface, ensuring proper capture of near-wall flow physics. By segmenting the domain, computational resources were optimised, coarser elements in less critical areas reduced unnecessary cell count, while finer meshing near the aerofoil improved flow feature resolution. This structured-unstructured hybrid approach ensured

efficient yet high-fidelity CFD analysis, particularly for viscous flow, boundary layer prediction, and wake interaction studies.

Table 1: Mesh independence study – Meshing parameters and spatial domains

Element Size	Number of Nodes (outer domain)	Number of Elements (outer domain)	Number of Inflation Layers (airfoil surface)	First Layer Height	Spatial Domain
0.1 m	28664	28369	20	6.648e-006 m	Region 1
0.05 m	111517	114355	30	6.648e-006 m	Neglected
0.009 m	137176	254297	40	6.648e-006 m	Region 2
0.004 m	550296	1061083	40	6.648e-006 m	Neglected

Table 2: Close-up view of the mesh near the airfoil, illustrating coarse, medium, and fine mesh regions

Coarse (element sizing of 0.05)	Medium (element sizing of 0.009 m)	Refined (element sizing of 0.004 m)

3.2.1.4 Geometry Modification

Following clean case simulations, aerofoil surface was modified by addition of dimple patterns shown in Figure 7. NACA 4412 with dimple geometries, including semi-circular, rectangular, trapezoidal, and triangular shapes were considered to assess their impact on turbulent flow behaviour and lift-drag performance. In this study, circular dimples with a diameter of 3.2% chord length and a depth of 1.6% diameter. Rectangular single and dual dimples with dimensions of 2.5% chord diameter and 1.1% depth. To minimise flow interruption and maximise potential aerodynamic advantages, the chosen dimple dimensions were customised and applied to NACA 4412 aerofoil suction surface. The study offered insights into the best surface texturing for drag reduction by experimenting with various shapes.

3.2.1.5: Modified Surface Mesh

The modified aerofoil requires a finer mesh in order to capture the flow physics and wake formation around dimple, so the region around the dimple was refined further as shown in Figure 8. A face sizing of 0.004 m was applied, and the rest of the mesh was similar to the clean case.

3.2.1.6 Solver Configuration

This section outlines the ANSYS Fluent solver setup for simulating viscous flow around the wing and domain.

3.2.1.6.1 RANS Turbulence Model

Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) are time-averaged equations used to simulate turbulent flow. By Reynolds decomposition technique, RANS equations are derived from Navier-Stokes equations. It decomposes flow variables into turbulent (fluctuating) components of fluid velocity in order to predict mean flow properties. Turbulent components include the Reynolds stress tensor, and to solve the equation, the concept of eddy viscosity was used. This simplifies the Reynolds stress tensor by connecting the stress term to turbulent kinetic energy.

The Shear Stress Transport (SST) $k-\omega$ is a two-equation eddy viscosity turbulence model frequently employed in engineering applications due to its computational efficiency and precision. This model addresses two transport equations $k-\omega$ and $k-\epsilon$ and integrate them, employing $k-\omega$ in the inner boundary layer region and transitioning to $k-\epsilon$ in the outer region characterised by free shear flow, as depicted in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Transition between $k-\omega$ and $k-\epsilon$ formulations in the SST $k-\omega$ turbulence model, demonstrating the shift from inner to outer boundary layer regions [17].

Table 3: The comparison between two different turbulence model

Key Features of Turbulence Models	K-Epsilon	K-Omega/SST
Near-wall resolution	Requires damping functions in viscous sublayer ($y^+ < 5$)	Resolves viscous sublayers (low Reynolds number) and does not require damping functions (y^+ can be approx. to 1)
Adverse pressure gradients	Overpredict flow separation	Accurately predict flow separation near the wall
Free stream sensitivity	Robust to inlet conditions	Highly sensitive
Common applications	External aerodynamics; automotive such as bluff bodies and pipe flow	Internal flows such as pipe, turbomachinery, wings, or aerofoils etc

Hence, SST k - ω turbulence model was selected for its accuracy in resolving adverse pressure gradients and boundary layer separation, critical for capturing stall dynamics and wake interactions. This turbulence model combines both continuity and momentum equations of fluid dynamics with two additional transport equations for turbulence kinetic energy (k) and specific dissipation rate (ω).

Below are the governing equations:

Continuity equation (assuming the flow is incompressible ρ is constant: $\nabla \cdot u = 0$):

$$\frac{\partial t}{\partial \rho} + \nabla \cdot (\rho u) = 0 \quad (1)$$

Reynolds-Averaged Momentum Equation:

$$\frac{\partial(\rho u)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho u u) = -\nabla p + \nabla \cdot [(\mu + \mu_t)(\nabla u + (\nabla u)^T - \frac{2}{3}(\nabla \cdot u)I)] + f \quad (2)$$

K Omega SST Transport Equations [17]:

$$\frac{\partial(k)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (uk) = \nabla \cdot ((\mu + \sigma_k \mu_t)\nabla k) + P_k - \beta^* \omega k \quad (3)$$

- Turbulence Kinetic Energy (k):
- P_k : Production term ($P_k = \mu_t S^2$, $S = \sqrt{2S_{ij}S_{ij}}$)
- σ_k : Diffusion coefficient (blended between k - ω and k - ϵ models)
- $\beta^* = 0.09$: Model constant

Specific Dissipation Rate [17] (ω):

$$\frac{\partial(\rho\omega)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho u \omega) = \nabla \cdot ((\mu + \sigma_\omega \mu_t) \nabla \omega) + \frac{\gamma \rho}{\nu_t} P_k - \beta \rho \omega^2 + 2(1 - F_1) \frac{\rho \sigma_\omega}{\omega} \nabla k \cdot \nabla \omega \quad (4)$$

- γ, β : blended constants which depends on F_1 , blending function (k - ω model near walls $F_1 = 1$, k - ϵ model in free stream $F_1 = 0$)

Turbulent Viscosity (ν_t) with SST model becomes:

$$\nu_t = \frac{a_1 k}{\max(a_1 \omega, SF_2)} \quad (5)$$

- $a_1 = 0.31$ (constant) and F_2 : second blending function (limits ν_t in high-strain regions)

The model utilises a Re of 3×10^6 and dynamic viscosity (ν) of 1.78×10^{-6} . A target y^+ value of 1 was enforced, with the first cell height (y) calculated as:

$$y^+ = \frac{y u^*}{\nu} \quad (6)$$

where the friction velocity (u^*) is derived from the skin friction coefficient (C_F):

$$u^* = \frac{\tau_w}{\rho} = \sqrt{\frac{C_F}{2}}, \quad C_F = \frac{0.059}{Re^{\frac{1}{5}}} \quad (7)$$

This yielded a first-layer thickness of $8.47 \mu\text{m}$ (8.47×10^{-6} m), ensuring adequate boundary layer resolution.

3.2.1.6.2 Boundary Conditions

Boundary conditions are essential for solving the computational problem. Initially, the Inlet, Outlet, Farfield, and Aerofoil wall were selected, and the detailed applied boundary conditions are described in the table 4 below.

Table 4: summary of all the applied boundary conditions		
Parameter	Value/Setting	Description
Flow Properties		
Freestream velocity at inlet	43.689 m/s	Speed of incoming flow in freestream direction
Fluid density	1.225 kg/m ³	Air density at standard atmospheric conditions
Dynamic viscosity	1.7894×10^{-5} kg/(m·s)	Viscosity for incompressible flow

Reynolds number (Re)	3,000,000	Turbulent flow
Boundary Conditions		
turbulence intensity	$I = 0.16Re^{1/8} = 0.025$	External flow is viscous, low turbulence
Outlet turbulence viscosity ratio	10	Controls the eddy viscosity at domain exit
Outlet gauge pressure	0 Pa	Static pressure at outlet relative to ambient
Solver properties		
Solver type	Pressure-based solver	Solves pressure-velocity coupling for steady-state flow which makes flow quicker to converge
Gradient scheme	Least squares cell-based	Spatial gradient calculation method
Pressure scheme	standard	Discretisation for pressure field
Momentum scheme	Second order upwind	High-accuracy spatial discretisation for velocity
Turbulence Kinetic Energy and dissipation rate	Second-order upwind (k, ω)	Accurate resolution of turbulent kinetic energy and dissipation rate
Turbulence Model (SST k-ω)		
Eddy viscosity limiter (a_1)	0.31	Prevents overprediction of turbulence near separation
Turbulence closure coefficient (β^*)	0.09	Couples' turbulent kinetic energy (k) and specific dissipation rate (ω)
Near-wall blending coefficient (γ_1)	5/9	Activates k- ω behaviour in boundary layers
Free-stream blending coefficient (γ_2)	0.44	Transitions to k- ϵ behaviour in outer flow regions
Turbulent diffusion (σ_k)	0.85	Dissipation rate of k in near-wall regions
Turbulent diffusion (σ_ω)	0.5	Dissipation rate of ω in near-wall regions

The x and y velocity components were adjusted to simulate varying angles of attack. The CFD setup modifies the flow direction while keeping the aerofoil geometry fixed. This approach alters the incoming flow angle to replicate different aerodynamic conditions. At higher angles of attack, solver convergence becomes challenging; to address this, the momentum discretisation scheme was shifted from second order to first-order upwind. This adjustment improves computational efficiency by stabilising the solver and accelerating convergence.

The reference pressure point was defined at 1 m upstream of the leading edge in the free-stream direction. The stagnation pressure point was positioned within the domain's stable flow region to ensure accurate representation of flow behaviour. For flow convergence the residual monitor was set to $1e^{-6}$ which shows that the flow converges as all the continuity, x velocity, y velocity and k and omega equations stabilises near the set value.

3.2.2 Validation Against Prior Studies

A validation study was conducted in this research to assess the accuracy, reliability, and methodological consistency of the approach, ensuring alignment with peer-reviewed literature. The validation results were compared against those reported in the paper "*Computational Study of Aerodynamic Flow over NACA 4412 Airfoil*" by Petinrin, M. a. [12]. While the referenced study examined a range of Reynolds numbers and aerofoil configurations, the primary focus of the study is to mirror their work at Reynolds of 3,000,000 utilising the NACA 4412 aerofoil.

The 2D computational model of the NACA 4412 aerofoil, with a chord length of 1 m, incorporated boundary conditions such as a pressure outlet and velocity inlet. Air properties, including density, were defined using standard atmospheric conditions (ATM) as outlined in the preceding section. Key aerodynamic performance metrics, C_L , C_D , and the L/D for efficiency, were evaluated and cross-verified with the published study.

Figure 10: Comparison of C_L vs AoA clean NACA aerofoil study with high Reynolds Number 3,000,000

Figure 11: Comparison of C_D vs AoA at high Reynolds Number 3,000,000

The findings of this study align closely with the work of Petinrin (M. A.) [12], as illustrated in Figures 10 and 11. The data from the referenced study were digitized using the *WebPlotDigitizer* tool (automeris.io) and post-processed in Python. Minor deviations observed between the datasets may root from manual inaccuracies during plot digitisation or differences in mesh refinement, this study employed a finer mesh near the wall compared to the coarser mesh used by Petinrin so better boundary layer transition are captured.

XFOIL analysis of the NACA4412 aerofoil was conducted at matching Reynolds numbers. While XFOIL results for C_L and C_D at low AoA align reasonably with Petinrin's data, discrepancies emerge at higher AoAs. As shown in Figure 10, XFOIL overpredicts C_L and underpredicts C_D beyond 10° AoA. This divergence arises because XFOIL assumes steady, irrotational, and incompressible 2D flow, for simplicity as it fails to capture turbulent

wake formation and rotational effects at elevated AoAs. Consequently, XFOIL predicts an unrealistically delayed stall angle of 16° , whereas Petinrin's ANSYS Fluent simulations (validated experimentally) confirm stall initiation at 14° . Despite these limitations, XFOIL remains a useful tool for rapid preliminary analysis at low AoAs.

3.2.3 Study 1: Varying Shape of Dimple at Constant Location

The first study analysed how an aerofoil's shape affected the aerodynamic performance. Only a dimple modification at precisely location served as the basis for this study. First a clean NACA 4412 were simulated to analyse the flow separation point determined by analysing velocity contours and velocity vectors. Flow separation point is determined where there is a sharp decrease in skin friction which can be found from analysing skin friction coefficient plots. While conducting clean case simulation for comparison, it was determined that flow starts to separate near 6° . Moreover, since the stalling angle is between 10 and 15 degrees, the research specifically focused on all angles of attack between 6 and 20 degrees. The TKE contours were plotted to analyse the turbulent wake and the clean case plots were compared with the dimpled case.

A dimple with varying shapes were modelled throughout an AoA range of 0° to 20° , and its C_L and C_D were recorded. Rectangle, semi-circle, triangle and trapezoid shapes of dimple were selected for the study. After modifying the NACA 4412 aerofoil with these shapes, the four modified aerofoils with their geometries and applied suitable meshing, as previously mentioned were simulated using Ansys Fluent. Only the impacts of shapes would be investigated because all modifications were made at a controlled position.

3.2.4 Study 2: Varying Dimple Position at Constant Shape

In this study, dimple positions were adjusted along the aerofoil's chord. They were repositioned from (0.1c) near the LE to (0.9c) near the TE. Like the previous study, the simulations were conducted from 0° to 20° AoA. This study focuses on varying dimple locations from 0.1c to 0.9c, and the C_L , C_D and L/D were recorded. This spatial analysis is used to identify the optimal chordwise positions of dimple. The resulting data trends and their aerodynamic implications are presented in the following section.

3.2.5 Study 3: Dual-Dimple Optimisation by Varying Position

Finally, this study extends the findings of Studies 1 and 2, which identified the optimal dimple shape and single-dimple placement for aerodynamic improvement. Leveraging these results, two dimples were added, positioned near the LE and TE of the NACA4412 aerofoil. The distance between the dimples was incrementally reduced to analyse the aerodynamic effects of bringing dimples closer to each other. Simulations were conducted across AoA range of 0° – 20° , with a focus on quantifying performance metrics such as L/D, stall behaviour, and wake dynamics.

The flow characteristics were analysed using pressure distributions and velocity contours to map flow acceleration, separation points, and wake structures. Turbulent kinetic energy (TKE) plots were evaluated pre- and post-stall to assess energy dissipation and boundary layer reattachment potential. This dual-dimple configuration aimed to delay stall by modifying adverse pressure gradients and enhancing flow attachment downstream of the dimples. Performance outcomes were benchmarked against the clean aerofoil and prior single-dimple cases to determine the optimal dual-dimple arrangement for maximising aerodynamic efficiency.

3.3.6 Three-Dimensional (3D) Setup

The findings of the 2D study were immediately followed by the 3D study. The NACA4412 aerofoil and its optimised surface modification(s) were extruded into 3D space and examined under comparable conditions, see Figure 12.

(I)

(II)

(III)

Figure 12: Subfigure (I), (II), and (III) depicts isometric clean wing, equally spaced dual dimple and spanwise extruded dual dimple modified NACA 4412

3.3.6.1 Wing Domain

The 3D wing was designed based on the Aeronca 11 AC specifications, which prescribe an aspect ratio of 7.25. For a chord length (c) of 1 m, the full-scale span would equate to 7.25 m; however, to reduce computational expense, a half-span model (4 m) was implemented. This approach leverages symmetry boundary conditions at the wing root, effectively halving the mesh cell count while preserving flow physics accuracy. The (NACA 4412) aerofoil geometry was extruded along the 4 m semi-span, and the fluid domain (illustrated in Figure 13) extended 8 m longitudinally (twice the wingspan), as recommended by Elham et al. [4] to minimise boundary interference.

A refinement zone (Region 4), a cuboid depth of 0.5 m from the wing centreline, 3 m vertically, and 4.5 m horizontally, was embedded within the domain to prioritise mesh resolution in critical flow regions. The wing's upper surface was partitioned into three sections, from the stagnation point to 0.15 from LE, 0.20 m from TE and 0.65m in between LE and TE. This partitioning enabled mesh refinement near the LE and TE, where curvature and boundary layer gradients are steepest, ensuring precise capture of flow separation, wake development, and pressure distributions.

Figure 13: illustrates 3D computational domain and wing

3.3.6.2 Wing and Domain Meshing

A test simulation was conducted to compare the orthogonality, aspect ratio C_L and C_D for all three types of meshes (see Table 5 and 6) and it was noticed that the C_L and C_D values of medium and refined mesh were closer to each other, but the medium mesh took less computational time. Thus, it was concluded that the medium mesh is good for the dimple optimisation research purposes.

Table 5: comparing different mesh types and quality

Type	Aspect Ratio	Orthogonality
Coarse Mesh		
Medium Mesh		
Refined Mesh		

Based on the mesh independent study, face sizing of 0.1 m was applied on region 1. Regions 2 and 3 were the upper surface leading and trailing edge and face sizing of 0.002 m were applied on both regions. The reason for the refinement was that leading and trailing edge often experience sharp changes in pressure, velocity and boundary layer resolution. Thus, the mesh was refined to accurately capture high pressure, velocity gradients. This is critical for predicting accurate lift and drag coefficients. Moreover, the face sizing of 0.003 m was applied on the middle upper surface and lower surface as mesh refinement enhances solver stability and reduces numerical errors ensuring smoother flow prediction.

Table 6: depicts all three mesh types on the domain and wing

Type	Domain	Close view
Coarse Mesh		
Medium Mesh		
Refined mesh		

3.3.6.3 Fluent Solver Configuration

In this 3D investigation, the aerofoil geometry was constructed in the y-z plane, with the wingspan oriented along the x-axis. Consequently, the inlet velocity components were aligned with the y- and z-directions to match the aerofoil's planar orientation. The full-scale wingspan measured 7.25 m, and the reference wing area (A) was calculated using the standard relationship:

$$A = s \times c, \text{ where span (s) and chord (c)} \quad (8)$$

yielded a reference area of 7.25 m².

To optimise computational efficiency, the geometry was linearly scaled by a factor of 0.25 while preserving aerodynamic similarity. This reduction resulted in a modified span of 1.87 m and aerofoil chord length of 0.25 m. The scaled configuration retained geometric proportionality to ensure fidelity in flow dynamics while significantly lowering simulation resource requirements.

3.3.6.4: Modified Wing and Domain

Starting from the clean wing, dual-dimples were added based on the Study 3 but at a spanwise spacing of 125 mm, as shown in Figure 12 (II). Another configuration includes extruding the surface depicted in Figure 12 (III). The following section comprehensively examines the meshing strategy and its effects.

3.3.6.5: Modified Wing Mesh

For extruded dual-dimple mesh, face sizing of 0.0004 m applied on the dimple surface and edge sizing with 800 number of divisions and bias of 1000 were applied for mesh demonstrated in Table 7. For second study (equally spaced dual dimple) the face sizing of 0.00009 m on dimple surfaces, edge sizing with 1000 divisions and bias of 2000 was applied shown in Table 8. Orthogonality and aspect ratio from mesh independence study shows that the mesh is refined enough to analyse the flow behaviour near dimples.

3.3.6.7: Study 4: Dual-Dimple Wing Density

As mentioned above two dimpled wing configurations were tested in this study: one with uniformly spaced dimple at 125 mm intervals and another employing spanwise extruded dimple. The purpose of the study is to determine if excessive dimple density elevates skin friction drag which can affect aerodynamic performance (reducing L/D ratio).

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Two-Dimensional Findings

The 2D study evaluated the flow behaviour at various AoA ranging from 0° to 20° , with emphasis on identifying critical flow separation regions. At the stalling angle of 14° , flow detachment was observed, accompanied by a decrease in C_L growth. In contrast, attached flow regimes dominated at lower AoAs ($0^\circ - 8^\circ$), where C_L increases linearly as demonstrated in Graph 1 (C_L vs AoA). These results map the transition from stable boundary layer adherence to premature separation, leading to need of surface modification. Hence NACA 4412 was modified as explained in Section 3, with dimples at flow separation points. A variation in pressure gradients and flow behaviour was noticed, so the results of clean case are compared with the modified aerofoil to better understand the flow aerodynamics.

In the velocity contours (Table 9 below), increasing the AoA indicating flow detachment from the surface (blue region). From 14° to 20° a collapse in velocity near the TE, accompanied by pressure fluctuations in pressure contours (see Appendix Table 22) indicating flow separation. The transition causes rapid lift reduction and drag increase due to disrupted streamlines and increased turbulent kinetic energy dissipation (red region near aerofoil) can be visualised in TKE contours (see Appendix Table 24).

Table 9: velocity contours for clean NACA 4412 visualising flow behaviour

Skin friction plots (Table 10 below) confirmed flow separation initiation points at critical chordwise locations (0.1c, 0.35c, 0.55c, 0.75c, and 0.9c) for varying AoAs. These points were chosen for dimple addition, with the purpose of the study to examine if surface modifications can postpone the stall by the reattachment of boundary layer.

Table 10: skin friction coefficient plots for clean NACA 4412 indicating separation

4.1.1: Study 1: Varying Shape of Dimple at Constant Location

This study shows how varying dimple geometry can influence flow behaviour. The trapezoidal, triangle, rectangular, and semi-circular dimples at chordwise positions of 0.55c and 0.75c regions are tested first as these regions are near the stalling angle. Aerodynamic evaluation revealed trapezoidal dimples produced the poorest lift-to-drag ratios, prompting their exclusion from subsequent studies. Subsequent tests were conducted placing dimples at 0.35c and 0.9c (close to TE), followed by a final case at 0.1c (close to LE). The results shown in Graph 1 to 5 below, identified rectangular dimple as the optimal configuration, achieving improved L/D ratio compared to the clean aerofoil. The contours and streamlines were also recorded in the tables below which indicates how boundary layer flow separation delays and vortex interaction enhance compared to the clean case.

(I)

(II)

(III)

Graph 1: (I), (II), and (III) depict the C_L , C_D , and L/D profiles, respectively, for the dimple configuration positioned at the $0.55c$ chordwise location

(I)

(II)

(III)

Graph 2: (I), (II), and (III) depict the C_L , C_D , and L/D profiles, respectively, for the dimple configuration positioned at the $0.75c$ chordwise location.

(I)

(II)

(III)

Graph 3: (I), (II), and (III) depict the C_L , C_D , and L/D profiles, respectively, for the dimple configuration positioned at the $0.35c$ chordwise location.

(I)

(II)

(III)

Graph 4: (I), (II), and (III) depict the C_L , C_D , and L/D profiles, respectively, for the dimple configuration positioned at the $0.35c$ chordwise location.

(I)

(II)

(III)

Graph 5: (I), (II), and (III) depict the C_L , C_D , and L/D profiles, respectively, for the dimple configuration positioned at the $0.10c$ chordwise location.

Pressure and velocity contours (see Table 11) for the rectangular dimple case at 0.55c evaluating pre- and post-stall. The pressure contours and velocity vectors verify vortex generation close to the dimple. A flow separation bubble forms where the flow briefly detaches, highlighted by a blue region in the pressure contour, followed by reattachment near the TE. The abrupt rise in the pressure in post-stall contour signifies turbulence. This confirms that the dimple delay flow separation and creates wake and improving aerodynamic performance in comparison to the clean aerofoil.

Table 11: Rectangular dimple at 0.55c pre and post stall (6° and 20°) results	
Pressure contour	
TKE contour	
Velocity Magnitude Vector	
Skin Friction plot	

Figure 14 shows the pressure distribution of modified aerofoils compared to clean aerofoil at 6° and 18° AoA (representing pre and post stall). On the suction surface, due to dimples there is a spike in the plots. In contrast to the trapezoidal case, the rectangular dimple shows a longer negative pressure area (wider suction region) on the upper surface at 6° AoA, which implies delayed boundary layer separation and continued flow acceleration. As positive pressure gradient over an aerofoil chord is maintained with wider area, this increases lift generation. In comparison to the trapezoidal dimple, due to the narrower shape the flow accelerates with minimal subsequent pressure recovery, causes early flow separation and insufficient vortex formation.

At 18° AoA (post-stall) rectangular dimple suction curve is comparatively wider than clean aerofoil curve, the sudden drop and rise in pressure near 1.55 m ($0.55c$) is a sign of turbulent flow reattachment thus improving stall characteristics. However, rear upper surface of trapezoidal shape dimpled aerofoil shows rapid collapse (abrupt change in positive pressure), which implies to flow detachment. Thus, unstable separation due to losses in energy increases drag while lowering L/D ratio for trapezoidal shape dimple outweighing any aerodynamic benefits.

Figure 14: Pressure distribution plots pre and post stall 6° and 18° compared with clean case

4.1.2 Study 2: Varying Dimple Position at Constant Shape

Study 1 investigated the aerodynamic performance of various dimple geometries and demonstrated that rectangular dimples provide the optimal results. Building on this finding, rectangular dimples were implemented at different locations on the surface. The results revealed that placing dimples near the LE ($0.1c$) and TE ($0.9c$) regions significantly increased drag. Although these configurations generated higher lift forces, the substantial drag increase ultimately compromised overall aerodynamic efficiency.

The results of rectangular dimple at $0.75c$ at 20° (depicted in Table 12) provide strong evidence that this aerofoil modification successfully delay flow separation which results in

reduced drag compared to the clean case. The absence of rapid colour change from green to orange at the suction surface means that no sharp adverse pressure gradient regions. The green circular region (in TKE contour) near the TE strongly suggests vortex formation, indicating control pressure recovery zone.

Velocity vector (see Table 13 below) shows clear flow separation with rectangular dimple at 0.35c, near TE at 20 degrees. As the vector points away from the surface it shows reverse flow which is a sign of stall.

(I)

(II)

(III)

Graph 6: (I), (II), and (III) depict the C_L , C_D , and L/D profiles, respectively, for the rectangular dimple configuration varying position.

Graph 6 demonstrates that dimples at 0.75c, 0.55c and 0.35c performed better than the dimples at LE (0.1c) and TE (0.9c). Moreover, it also reveals that the stall was delayed with dimple at 0.75c with stalling angle reaches up to 16 degrees whereas the clean NACA 4412 stalling angle is around 14 degrees.

The rectangular dimple at 0.10c (Appendix Table 26) demonstrate a gradual increase in adverse pressure gradient at low AoA (pre stall) however, higher AoA results in higher drag and there is no justification of flow reattachment. Moreover, contours of rectangular dimple at 0.90c (see Appendix Table 25) demonstrates high TKE region near the TE, and there is no evidence that shows flow is reattaching after separation. Moreover,

4.1.3: Study 3: Dual-Dimple Optimisation by Varying Position

The findings of the Study 2 showed that dimples placed at LE and TE increased drag, hence dimples at 0.1c and 0.9c were ignored. This study involved keeping one dimple at fixed location while varying the position of the other dimple. First the dimple near TE was kept at 0.75c and the dimple near LE was moved from 0.35c to 0.45c, the drag was increased as the dimples were placed closer to one another. More specifically, the dual dimple configuration at 0.35c and 0.75c produced more drag and less lift than the 0.45c and 0.75c dimples. Likewise, holding the dimple at 0.35c and shifting the second dimple from 0.55c to 0.40c validated decreased dimple spacing increases drag thus reducing L/D ratio. Based on these trends, the dual-dimple arrangement at 0.35c and 0.75c on the suction surface proved to be aerodynamically optimal. An examination of static pressure, TKE, velocity magnitude for pre and near stall AoAs – 6 and 16 flow demonstrated that it postpones flow separation and stall onset relative to clean aerofoil, illustrating dimples potential for improving stall characteristics.

(I)

(II)

(III)

Graph 7: (I), (II), and (III) depict the C_L , C_D , and L/D profiles, for the rectangular dual dimple while varying position.

The dimpled surface delay flow separation by increasing boundary layer reattachment downstream of the first dimple. Velocity contours and streamlines (see Table 14 above) at 14°-16° AoA show that following dimple 1, vortices energise the boundary layer, forcing flow to reattach and stick to the surface. At 16° AoA, the separation points shift by

approximately 0.1c aft from 14°, reducing the turbulent wake formation and enhancing pressure recovery.

4.1.4: Verification of Mesh Adequacy Using y^+ Analysis:

The comparison between clean and dual-dimpled aerofoil y^+ values shows that the maximum y^+ at the LE for the clean aerofoil is 1.1, whereas for the dual-dimpled aerofoil, it is 1.05 (depicted in Table 15). Due to the presence of dimples on the suction surface, the data exhibits a drop in y^+ values at these features. Since the target y^+ was set to 1, and the results demonstrate that y^+ remains within acceptable range, this concludes that the mesh resolution was adequate for the simulation purposes.

In the study, maintaining appropriate y^+ values (around 1) was critical for accurately resolving the boundary layer especially when analysing dimples effect on flow separation and transition. The slight difference in clean vs dimpled aerofoil y^+ indicate the mesh quality was kept consistent while capturing the flow effects due to dimples.

Table 15: wall y^+ plus plot for 6° and 16° AoA

	AoA – 6°	AoA – 16°
Clean NACA 4412		
Dual dimpled NACA 4412		

4.2 Three-dimensional Findings

Using the parameters explained in Section 3.3.6, the results of the 3D simulations for the smooth (clean) surface and the dimpled surface were compared. The findings are visualized in the contour plots below.

4.2.1 Study 4: Dual-Dimple Variable Wing Density

This study extends the scope of Study 3 by analysing a 3D wing model with variations in dimple density. Rectangular dimples spanwise extruded positioned at 0.35c and 0.75c chord locations, demonstrated a C_L rise of 26% compared to the clean wing at 16 AoA (stalling angle). Results revealed (see Graph 8) minimal divergence in lift performance between equally spaced and extruded dimple designs, with only a 4% difference in maximum C_L . However, the drag of the equally spaced dimpled wing was notably higher than that of the extruded dimpled wing, suggesting that extruded dimples offer a more favourable balance between lift increase and drag reduction.

(I)

(II)

(III)

Graph 8: (I), (II), (III) illustrated lift coefficient, drag coefficient and L/D vs angle of attack

Table 16 below demonstrates, the comparison of pressure distributions on the top and bottom surfaces reveals that the spanwise extruded dual-dimple wing generates the lowest pressure on the suction surface. This effect correlates with an increase in pressure drag, which explains why the extruded dimpled configuration exhibits higher overall drag compared to other design.

Table 16: pressure contours of dimpled vs clean case

Isometric view	Top View	Bottom view
Pressure contour Clean Wing – AoA 14°		
Pressure contour Equally Spaced Dual-Dimple – AoA 14°		
Pressure contour Spanwise Extruded Dual-Dimple – AoA 14°		

At a 14° AoA, the clean dimple surface allows the flow to remain attached longer and flow stays laminar. In contrast, the equally spaced dual-dimple configuration causes earlier flow separation as the flow become turbulent. Moreover, velocity contours show that the equally spaced dimples produce higher velocity on the suction surface, likely due to increased acceleration and flow disturbance. Meanwhile, the spanwise extruded dimple results in lower velocity on the suction surface, indicating less flow acceleration and possibly more stable boundary layer behaviour (see Table 17).

Table 17: velocity contour for all the three cases

Velocity contours	Clean Wing – AoA 14°	Equally Spaced Dual-Dimple – AoA 14°	Spanwise Extruded Dual-Dimple – AoA 14°
Cross Sectional View			

At 14° AoA, smooth streamlines (see Table 18) in streamwise velocity direction indicate laminar flow near the root section, suggesting minimal boundary layer separation. However, velocity swirls (curls) observed at the tip imply 3D flow effects, likely due to tip vortices or early-stage turbulence. Equally spaced dual-dimple generates stronger tip swirls compared to spanwise-extruded dimples. This occurs because dual dimple disrupts the flow more uniformly, enhancing vortex generation. In contrast, spanwise-extruded dimple promotes aligned vorticity, reducing tip turbulence.

Table 18: velocity streamlines on wing for all the three cases at 14-degree AoA

Both the equally spaced and spanwise-extruded dual-dimple cases indicate similar flow behaviour and pressure distribution at this angle (demonstrated in Table 19). This indicates that, at higher angles of attack, the specific arrangement of dual-dimple has less influence on the overall flow pattern, likely because flow separation becomes more dominant and overwhelms the subtle effects of dimple geometry.

Table 19: pressure contour for all the three cases at 20-degree AoA

At 20° AoA, from the velocity contours (in Table 20) at the root the velocity is higher for the spanwise-extruded dual-dimple compared to the clean wing. This suggests that the spanwise-extruded dimple energise the boundary layer near the root, helping to delay separation and maintain higher local flow velocities. In contrast, the clean wing likely experiences laminar flow at the root, resulting in lower velocities in this region.

Table 20: velocity contour for all the three cases

Velocity contours	Clean Wing – AoA 20°	Equally Spaced Dual-Dimple – AoA 20°	Spanwise Extruded Dual-Dimple – AoA 20°
Cross Sectional View			

At 20° AoA, the clean wing case produces strong tip vortices demonstrated in Table 21, which might be due to high pressure differences and flow separation near the tip. In contrast, the spanwise-extruded dual-dimple configuration shows additional swirls along the span, not just at the tip. This indicates that the dimples introduce flow disturbances, promoting tiny vortex formation and potentially energising the boundary layer and delaying separation.

Table 21: velocity streamlines on wing for all the three cases at 20-degree AoA

Isometric view	Zoomed in tip View
Velocity Streamlines for Clean Wing – AoA 20°	

5. Applications of Dimples on NACA 4412 Aerofoil and Future Research:

The NACA 4412 aerofoil widely used in sport and training aircrafts, because of its stable stall behaviour and predictable low-speed performance, helps pilot stall recovery and slow-flight manoeuvres. Aircraft like the Aeronca 65-TAC Defender, Aeronca 11AC Chief, and AI-AA2 Mamba use NACA 4412 due to its moderate camber to balance lift and drag for efficient cruising and better manoeuvrability [19]. These aircrafts can benefit from this research findings by placing rectangle dual-dimple at locations 0.35c and 0.75c which can improve their aerodynamic efficiency. However, wind tunnel testing is required before taking this research to the next step. Moreover, this innovation (dimple addition) could redefine safety protocols for training aircrafts and pilot getting greater error margins during high-risk scenarios. By integrating such modifications, flight schools may significantly reduce stall-related incidents, ensuring safer skill development while retaining the aerofoil's foundational reliability. Furthermore, Vintage aircrafts such as Mustang P51,

Lockhead P-38 lightning from World War II [19] retain NACA 4412 aerofoil due to aerofoil aerodynamic benefits.

Beyond the aviation industry, NACA 4412 aerofoil used in renewable energy small wind turbine blades [19] so addition of dimple patterns on the aerofoil might reduce energy dissipation and improve the aerodynamic efficiency. However similar research needs to be conducted, exploring scaling these dimple designs to higher Reynolds numbers relevant to turbine operation while adapting the computational domain to account for rotational effect and blade geometry. While initial dimple placement on turbine blades could leverage the location patterns validated in this study, offering a practical starting point for improving energy capture and reducing unsteady loads in wind energy applications. As hybrid blades design in turbines combines different aerofoil shapes to optimise performance so dual-dimple NACA 4412 aerofoil geometry based on research findings might be beneficial and more aerodynamically efficiency.

In automotive industry, the characteristics of NACA 4412 aerofoil for producing lift are being applied to race car spoilers, where dimples could optimise boundary layer control to maximise downforce and drag. Even emerging technologies like EVTOL (electric vertical take-off and landing) airplanes are employing the NACA 4412 aerofoil for fixed-wing segments, facilitating efficiency in hover-to-cruise regimes [20].

Crop dusting planes in agriculture rely on aerofoil's stable low speed performance for precision in spraying at low altitude [21] so NACA 4412 aerofoil can be considered. Hence, adding dimples to the aerofoil might improve aerodynamic performance and reduce fuel consumption, improve stability and manoeuvrability of the aircraft. As the aviation industry moves toward hybrid-electric propulsion the performance of NACA 4412 over the speed ranges could influence in future generation wing design optimising battery weight and lift demand. From the turbine blades to vintage fighter aircrafts, with the future of eVTOLs yet to come, this aerofoil decades old continue to change, becoming ageless amidst the times o changing technologies.

6. Conclusion

This study concludes that surface modifications using dimples with a depth of 1% of the chord and a length of 2.5% enhance aerodynamic performance, increasing the L/D ratio by 14.3% while delaying stall onset. Analysis of single and dual-dimple on NACA 4412 revealed distinct advantages: Studies 1 and 2 showed improved performance between 6° and 12° angles of attack (AoA), whereas Study 3 highlighted that dual-dimple, despite a slight reduction in C_L at low AoAs, effectively delayed stall by sustaining higher C_L values from 12° to 14° AoA. For 3D wing, positioning dual-dimple at 0.35c and 0.75c locations proved optimal, achieving a 26% increase in C_L at 16 AoA compared to the clean wing and further delaying flow separation. Notably, dual-dimple configurations, whether extruded through the wing or spaced uniformly, yielded comparable results, with less than a 5% variation in C_L , suggesting both designs warrant experimental validation through wind tunnel testing to refine dimple density.

The study conducted using the Aeronca 11 AC aircraft demonstrates that strategically designed dimples applied to the NACA4412 aerofoil enhance aerodynamic performance by delaying stall and improving the L/D ratio. While 2D simulations confirmed the stall-delaying mechanism through reduced flow separation, the 3D results from the modified aerofoil (delaying stall from 16° to 18°) encountered complexities linked to computational constraints, particularly in capturing full-span aerodynamic interactions and turbulence effects. Despite the aerofoil's inherently stable stalling behaviour—widely adopted in sport and training aircraft—this research underscores the need for further investigation under real-world conditions to validate the scalability of dimple-induced improvements. The promising 3D results, however, highlight the potential for safer, more efficient flight performance, bridging theoretical insights with practical aviation applications.

7. Limitations and Future Research

The NACA 4412 aerofoil has well-known predicted stall benefits in 2D: at low Reynolds number, the usual stalling angle ranges from 12° to 14° AoA. This study utilised the RANS SST k- ω turbulence model with a higher Reynolds number of 3 million which delays the stalling angle ranges from 14° to 16° AoA. Although computationally efficient, the model averages turbulent fluctuations and suppresses unstable vortices, which are crucial for understanding dynamic stall processes. This may result in overestimated lift coefficients due to underestimation of flow separation. The near-wall resolution ($Y^+ < 1$) and mesh refinement around dimples were prioritised, local grid sensitivity around dimpled regions may cause discretisation issues. Furthermore, the RANS framework ignores time-dependent flow physics by stabilising transient structures and disguising unsteady wake dynamics, as seen in the 3D streamline plots, which lacked fully turbulent reverse flow patterns.

To address these limitations, future studies could adopt scale-resolving methods like LES or DES coupled with transition models to better capture vortical structures and separation dynamics. While the current 3D simulations were constrained by computational resources (e.g., node limits on the Iridis 5 supercomputer), leveraging advanced GPU acceleration could enable finer meshes or transient analyses. A rigorous mesh independence study, alongside wind tunnel testing of the dimpled 3D wing, would strengthen confidence in the findings. Such experiments could also clarify whether the delayed stall observed in simulations translates to physical models, particularly for applications like sports and training aircrafts, where root/tip flow separation remains a critical challenge.

8. Appendix

Table 22: Pressure contours for clean case NACA 4412

Table 23: velocity vectors for clean case Velocity Vectors

Table 24: Turbulent Kinetic Energy contours for Clean Aerofoil

Table 25: Rectangular dimple at 0.90c pre and post stall (6° and 20°) results

Static Pressure contour

TKE contour

Velocity Magnitude Vectors

Skin Friction plots

Table 26: Rectangular dimple at 0.10c pre and post stall (6° and 20°) results

Static Pressure contour

TKE contour

Velocity Magnitude Vectors

Skin Friction plots


```
#!/bin/bash
#SBATCH --nodes=3
## set no. of nodes to use
#SBATCH --time=08:00:00
## set MAX runtime above (hh:mm:ss)
#SBATCH --ntasks=120
## on iridis you can run up to 40 tasks per node
module load fluent
srun hostname -s |sort -V > $(pwd)/slurmhosts.$SLURM_JOB_ID.txt
## leave the line above alone; idk what it does
## Run default version of Fluent in 2d double precision mode in parallel over
$SLURM_NTASKS processors
## Fluent commands are in __.jou file, output messages go to the output_file.
fluent 3ddp -t$SLURM_NTASKS -mpi=intel -pinfiniband -cnf=slurmhosts.$SLURM_JOB_ID.txt -
slurm -gu -i JournalFile0.jou > Output.txt
```

Table 27: presents the code used for the HPC WORKFILE job submission file.

```
;Reading in the case file (change to actual name in inverted commas)
/rc "file name"
;
/define/boundary-conditions/velocity-inlet inlet no yes yes no 0 yes no 0 no "free steam
velocity component (x)" no "velocity component (y)" no no yes no 1 0.025 10
;
/solve/monitors/force/lift-coefficient yes wing
yes no no no 0 0 1
;
/solve/monitors/force/drag-coefficient yes wing
yes no no no 0 1 0
;
/solve/initialize/initialize-flow
;
/solve/iterate 1000
;
;Exit Fluent
/exit yes
```

Table 28: presents the code used for the HPC SLURM job submission file

9. References

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